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HARBIN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY

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Numerical prediction and experimental analysis of the buckling loads of SMPC cylindrical shells

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SMPC cylindrical shell

➤ Shape Memory Polymer Composite (SMPC) is a kind of smart material with **shape memory effect** and **excellent mechanical properties**, which make it increasingly irreplaceable in **functional integrated components** of aerospace structures

- Imperfections**
- Geometric
 - loading
 - material

KDF: the ratio of the maximum axial load-bearing capacity of a cylindrical shell in practical applications to its theoretical critical buckling load

NASA (cylindrical shell): $KDF = 1 - 0.901 \times (1 - e^{-\sqrt{R/t}/16})$

Load-displacement curve and KDF of cylindrical shell

H Wagner, C Huhne, et al. Thin-Walled Structure, 2018, 127: 629-45.

Parameter study of the finite element model

- Key parameters, such as the **overall size**, **fiber stacking configurations** and **mesh size** should be first determined before the subsequent nonlinear finite element analyses and experiments
- **Dimensional parameter** $Z = 0.6L^2/Rh$

The mesh convergence study

The critical buckling loads as a function of Z

- $Z = 90$
- Fiber stacking configuration $[0/90/±45]_2$

Numerical simulations

➤ The single perturbation displacement imperfection (**SPDI**), multiple perturbation displacement imperfection (**MPDI**) and linear buckling mode imperfection (**LBMI**) techniques are introduced to verify the geometric imperfection sensitivities of SMPC cylindrical shells

The basic ideas of SPDI and MPDI techniques

➤ The geometrical imperfections are not localized in the axial direction, and the shapes of initial geometric imperfections are independent of temperature.

PDI → Linear buckling mode → LBMI

SPDI technique

(c) The end shortening of the cylindrical shell is the same

The results of the SPDI method

- $\eta = 1\text{ mm}$
- The buckling loads are sensitive to temperature
- The post-buckling patterns and KDFs are insensitive to temperature

MPDI technique

The results of the SPDI method

- $\eta = 1 \text{ mm}$
- MPDI will be represented by 3PDI-as

LBMI technique

- Scaling factor is 0.3
- The geometrical imperfections are localized in the axial direction

The results of the LBMI method

Initial imperfections							
Post-buckling patterns							
	SPDI	2PDI	3PDI-s	3PDI-as	4PDI	LBMI (25/40°C)	LBMI (40/60/80°C)

Buckling tests under axial compression

- Autoclave molding
- $[0/90/\pm 45]_2$
- Diameter is 40 mm, free length is 60 mm
- Isothermal buckling tests of SMPC cylindrical shells under axial compression

The fabrication of SMPC cylindrical shells

Specimen of SMPC cylindrical shell

Axial compressive test

Results of experimental and numerical analyses

- At low temperatures (25 °C and 40 °C), the SMPC cylindrical shell is more prone to brittle fracture than buckling deformation
- At high temperatures (60 °C, 80 °C and 100 °C), the SMPC cylindrical shell buckles before being destroyed

The initial shape and deformation morphologies

The axial compressive load–displacement curves

Conclusions

- In the **low-temperature region**, all three imperfection methods **overestimate** the load-bearing capacity and KDF
- In the **high-temperature region**, the SPDI method overestimates the KDFs; the KDFs calculated by the **MPDI** and **LBMI** techniques are **in good agreement with the experimental results**
- Only the **LBMI** method can **distinguish the influence of temperature on the post-buckling patterns**, and the corresponding post-buckling pattern is more consistent with the experiment

Experiment

SPDI

MPDI

LBMI

KDF from numerical simulations and experimental results

The post-buckling patterns of $[0/90/\pm 45]_s$ SMPC cylindrical shells in the high-temperature region

The assumption of application

- **Locking state**: effectively bear the prestress due to its characteristics of **large load carrying capacity** and **small axial deformation before failure**
- **Releasing prestress**: the SMPC cylindrical shell buckle and shorten under the action of pre-stress so that the **prestress can be smoothly unloaded**, and the **instantaneous impact** can be **significantly reduced**.
- **Return to initial shape**: reheated again to its T_g

- The buckling load decreases from 1.67 kN to 1.49 kN after 10 repeated “initial-buckled-recovery shape” cycles, which is a decrease of only 10%
- The SMPC cylindrical shell can return to its initial shape without any damage

The working process of the auxiliary vibration reduction structure of the space pyrotechnic releasing mechanism

The repeated experiment

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Thank you